

PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES AND PRACTICES FOR SCHOOL CHILDREN

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ANNOTATION

This research reports the main famous pedagogical approaches as well practices in the education system, especially, that of school children. It is probably the most heated topic among scholars as there are only a few accepted methods and thousands of possible methods offered by the researchers. In this paper work, I will describe my own points of views and give possible reasons why I think so.

Key words: right approaches, methods, pedagogy, lesson, organization;

INTRODUCTION

As the education system develops day by day, the demand for better education also increases significantly. Today, there are numerous methods, approaches, systems in the education system. One of the most significant one is pedagogical approaches. The main concentration of such approaches is not on the common things, but on the things that we rarely pay attention in the classroom. That include the personality, background, individual development, organization of the classroom and other likely things. Once all is accurate, teacher rarely face problems while teaching and significantly, students become really active and productive.

“Pedagogy is important because it gives teachers an insight into the best practices for a classroom setting.

It allows them to understand how different students learn so they can tailor their lesson to suit these needs.

As a result, this will improve the quality of their teaching as it will be well received by students. By being mindful of which theories you’re using, and how children are interacting with them, you can create more meaningful lesson plans. Understanding and implementing good pedagogy helps teachers reconnect with their pupils and builds a better, more collaborative, relationship. There is understanding from both parties so that you are working towards a shared goal.” (1;5)

Understanding The Aim of Pedagogical Approaches

We know that the word pedagogy comes from Greek word, which means someone to guide a person. So, I would say that pedagogy is the mixture of guidance, psychology and other stuff. And when it comes to pedagogical approaches, it may seem kind of difficult thing for many. However, let's look at other opinions about pedagogy itself. Pedagogy is crucial because it informs instructors about the finest classroom techniques. It enables them to comprehend how various pupils learn in order to modify their lessons to meet these requirements. As a result, the quality of their instruction will improve since pupils will respond positively. You may build more meaningful lesson plans by being aware of which theories you're utilizing and how your students interact with them. "Teaching and learning were formal and structured (teacher-centered pedagogy), it did not provide opportunities for children to demonstrate their creativity, exploration, and problem solving so that they could develop their potential and possibilities for life. From this line of argument, a study by Isaacs (2010) argued that education should no longer consist of imparting knowledge; it must instead take a new track seeking the release of children's potential, creativity, and problem solving. Importantly, children need to learn through practicing tasks rather than through listening and having to memorize" (Isaacs, 2010, Al-Zu'be, 2013, Herbert, 2004).

The Benefits of Pedagogical Approaches and Practices

Also, there are some benefits of having pedagogical approaches in the classroom and let's look at some of them:

1. Improved quality of the lesson;

When there is organization in the lesson, children also feel themselves in balance and will start becoming more receptive. They do all exercises with great quality and this boosts children's participation level in the lesson and literally, children will become active.

2. Better understanding, interesting lesson

Actually, as we mentioned above there are a range of pedagogical approaches, so it is natural that in the lesson itself also, teacher uses a number of approaches as he/she teach students looking at their individual levels, personal fractures and other stuff. In this case, as children see all the stuff being taught, they understand the lesson in a deeper way.

3. Can uplift any student in spite of their backgrounds

To be honest, there are some children with problems in their families and other problems in their lives, which prevents them from studying. For this reason, when a pedagogical approach is great, it can highly help children to get the motivation they want and clarify their way ahead. "The learners tend to have

an easier time studying in a child-centred teaching system because they have the freedom to engage in spontaneous learning and to learn from each other through interaction with peers and teachers/adults. With LCP children are actively involved since they work in groups or individually to arrive at the desired results. Children take part in communication with peers and adults/teachers, hence developing their communicative skills as they learn from their own or peer's mistakes" (Maldonado-Carreño and Votruba-Drzal, 2011, Massey, 2004).

So, there could be found hundreds of reasons why teachers should use pedagogical approaches in their lesson. For every teacher, it is as important as air to realize the benefits of using them in the learning zone for better education approaches.

CONCLUSION

To conclude, using pedagogical approaches rightly is really important and to get the best results, one should practice them a lot. One more thing, these approaches can have numerous benefits for both the teacher and the students. All the possible methods have been mentioned above as the views of the author.

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